

Preliminary Research on Spatial and Energy-group MGXS Homogenization for the TRIGA Mark II Reactor

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ABSTRACT

In all deterministic neutron transport calculations, generating accurate multi-group cross sections (MGXS) is a crucial step. However, the relationship between the number of energy groups or the spatial homogenization schemes and the resulting computational accuracy is not always strictly linear and can vary across different applications. Therefore, this study aims to identify an optimal combination of these parameters for the TRIGA Mark II research reactor, considering both the diffusion and SP3 approximations. First, OpenMC was employed to generate the MGXS and to provide a reference solution. OpenFOAM was utilized to implement both approximation methods. The effects of updating MGXS for different control rod (CR) positions, six distinct spatial homogenization partitioning schemes, and four energy-group structures were investigated. The results indicate that pin-by-pin spatial division and two-group energy division improve the solution accuracy in both methods. When the three CRs are fully inserted, the SP3 method nearly doubles the accuracy, yielding a deviation of 295.4 ± 17.0 pcm from the OpenMC reference, compared with 505.5 ± 17.0 pcm for the diffusion method. More high-energy groups results in larger deviations in both methods. This can be attributed to inter-group scattering combined with resonance effects. Moreover, the capability of the SP3 method to capture anisotropic effects is affected by the high-energy divisions and the CR position.

Keywords: Multi-group cross section; Deterministic neutron transport calculation; Spatial homogenization; Energy-group structures; TRIGA Mark II reactor

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite advances in computational power enabling widespread use of Monte Carlo (MC) methods for criticality and burnup calculations, deterministic neutron transport remains popular due to lower computational cost and suitability for transient analyses [1]. In deterministic transport calculations, accurate multi-group cross sections (MGXS) are crucial: spatial homogenization and energy-group condensation must be fine enough to capture key heterogeneities and local effects such as spatial self-shielding. Homogenization replaces detailed heterogeneous pin cells or assemblies—including fuel, cladding, and gap materials—with a uniform material that preserves the original neutronic properties [2].

Given the importance of proper homogenization, numerous studies have addressed this topic. Boyd et al. investigated the impact of a flux separability approximation using a PWR pin-cell benchmark, assuming that during MGXS generation the angular variation of the flux is independent of its energy

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dependence. With a deterministic approach, they observed a 200 pcm difference compared to reference MC results [3]. In subsequent work, they introduced three pin-wise spatial homogenization schemes using OpenMC to collapse the MGXS and capture inter-pin spatial self-shielding effects [4]. Kevenoky earlier proposed a superhomogenization (SPH) method to account for pin-cell heterogeneity in fuel assemblies [5]. Wang et al. developed a leakage-corrected SPH method, representing neutron leakage discrepancies between homogeneous and heterogeneous problems as absorption reaction rates; the method showed excellent accuracy and computational efficiency [6]. Conversely, Galia et al. introduced a dynamic homogenization method involving iterative coupling between core and assembly calculations, providing homogenization parameters that account for each assembly within the core [7]. Most studies have focused on large commercial PWRs, with little attention to small or micro reactors.

For MGXS generation, the commercial MC code Serpent includes methods such as infinite and B1 leakage-corrected critical spectra, as well as calculations of discontinuity factors, pin-power form factors, delayed neutron parameters, and total and partial albedo [1]. However, despite these capabilities, Serpent cannot autonomously determine an optimal homogenization for a given case. In addition, the Shift module of the commercial SCALE code is able to generate MGXS [8]. Moreover, the relationship between energy-group number or spatial homogenization scheme and computational accuracy is not strictly linear and varies by application. Reactor types such as small and micro-reactors are particularly sensitive to energy-group structure due to their distinct neutron spectra, meaning a finer energy discretization is not always preferable [9]. The TRIGA Mark II reactor, a compact system with an asymmetric core, passive operation, and pulse mode, serves as a test model. To minimize computational cost and memory use, identifying an optimal spatial and energy-group homogenization scheme for the TRIGA reactor is essential, laying the groundwork for multi-region, multi-physics coupling.

This work builds on previous verification and validation studies of the diffusion and SP3 approximations for the TRIGA reactor. Although many deterministic methods exist for MGXS generation, they rely on assumptions such as unlimited medium or leakage correction, introducing inherent limitations and motivating gradual refinement over time. This study employs the MC method using the OpenMC code due to its open-source nature and its use in previous studies [10]. While OpenMC lacks some computationally efficient MGXS methods available in Serpent, such as infinite and B1 leakage-corrected critical spectra, its standard direct Monte Carlo approach can generate MGXS with high accuracy, albeit at a higher computational cost, due to minimal reliance on discretization approximations.

2. MODELING AND METHODOLOGY

MGXS homogenization in space and energy is central to solve deterministic neutron transport, balancing accuracy and efficiency. This study extends the diffusion and SP3 solvers of [11] to multi-region problems based on OpenFOAM v9, with MGXS data and reference solutions generated using OpenMC v0.15.2 from ENDF/B-VII.1 continuous-energy nuclear data library. This study used a total of 6×10^5 particles over 200 cycles, with the first 100 inactive cycles to achieve convergence of the fission source. This configuration leads to a relative error below 2×10^{-4} for the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}).

2.1. Geometry Modelling

The TRIGA Mark II research reactor family is commonly used to validate numerical tools. This work considers the 250 kW TRIGA reactor at the University of Pavia, whose core contains 80 fuel pins: 50 are 101-type elements with burnable poison disks and aluminum cladding, and 30 are 103-type elements with stainless steel cladding. Both fuel types use a zirconium hydride (ZrH) matrix, providing a strong negative temperature reactivity coefficient. Three control rods (CRs) manage emergency shutdown (TRANS) and coarse (SHIM) and fine (REG) power regulation [10]. A detailed OpenMC core model was built [10], with this study adding the water pool (6.85 m high, 1.98 m diameter) to better capture neutron leakage (Figure 1). In OpenFOAM, the reactor was reconstructed from scratch according to

spatial homogenization needs, using a polyhedral mesh to discretize the computational domains.

Figure 1. The TRIGA reactor model; (a) top view of the entire model; (b) side view of the entire model; (c) top view of the core region; (d) Side view of the core region. Color legend: fuel-101 (pink), fuel-103 (brown), CRs (black), graphite (green), air (dark green), cladding (peachy), water (blue). Other thin components are not clearly visible.

2.2. Spatial Homogenization

The most critical region of the reactor is the active core, making detailed investigation of core division schemes essential. All other structures were divided into three parts (except in the one-region and pin-by-pin cases), while the core was partitioned uniformly (Figure 2). Six cases were considered: a single-core region; 104 regions corresponding to a pin-by-pin division; and four intermediate cases with 1, 2, 5, and 10 core regions. The same partitioning was applied in OpenMC to generate MGXS data. Vacuum boundaries were set at the outer surfaces in both OpenFOAM and OpenMC. An unstructured mesh was used in all cases to reduce discretization uncertainty, with cell sizes ranging from 0.0067 m to 0.03 m and a growth rate of 1.2, following ANSYS Fluent recommendations. The total cell count ranges from 1.2 million (single-region) to 3.3 million (pin-by-pin). Mesh-independence analysis is discussed in Sec. 3.

2.3. Energy-Group Homogenization

Although MGXS generation via MC is highly accurate, the optimal number of energy groups for deterministic transport still requires investigation to minimize computational cost while maintaining accuracy. The OpenMC MGXS generation procedures are given in Eq. (1)–(2). SP3 calculations with eight groups showed convergence difficulties, as the SP3 approximation solves two neutron moment equations and is more susceptible to stiffness, particularly with finer thermal-group divisions [12]. Therefore, this study uses a maximum of eight groups for diffusion and four for SP3 simulations (Table I). All simulations ran on a computing cluster with an Intel® Xeon® E5-2630 v3 CPU @ 2.40 GHz and 64 GB RAM, using 16 parallel CPU cores. Computational costs for all cases are summarized in Table I.

Figure 2. The diagrams of spatial homogenization; (a) top view of one-region core; (b) side view of one-region core; (c) top view of five-region core; (d) side view of five-region core.

$$\sigma_{X,g} = \frac{\int_V d\mathbf{r} \int_{4\pi} d\Omega \int_{E_{g-1}}^{E_g} dE \sigma_X(\mathbf{r}, E) \psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \Omega)}{\langle \phi \rangle}; \sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} = \frac{\langle \sigma_{s,0,g' \rightarrow g} \phi \rangle - \delta_{gg'} \sum_{g''} \langle \sigma_{s,1,g'' \rightarrow g} \phi \rangle}{\langle \phi \rangle}. \quad (1)$$

$$\langle \sigma_{s,\ell,g' \rightarrow g} \phi \rangle = \int_{\mathbf{r} \in V} d\mathbf{r} \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \int_{E_{g'-1}}^{E_{g'}} dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega \int_{E_{g-1}}^{E_g} dE P_\ell(\Omega \cdot \Omega') \times \sigma_s(\mathbf{r}, E' \rightarrow E, \Omega' \cdot \Omega) \psi(\mathbf{r}, E', \Omega'); \sigma_{s,\ell,g' \rightarrow g} = \frac{\langle \sigma_{s,\ell,g' \rightarrow g} \phi \rangle}{\langle \phi \rangle}. \quad (2)$$

Here, $\delta_{g,g'}$ is Dirac delta function. ϕ and ψ are neutron flux and angular flux. $\sigma_{X,g}$ is arbitrary MGXS. $\sigma_{s,g}$ is scattering moment element. $\sigma_{s,\ell,g' \rightarrow g}$ and P_ℓ are Legendre scattering moments and coefficient.

Table I. Different energy-group divisions (0-2E7 eV) and corresponding computational costs for pin-by-pin case.

Groups	Discrete point (eV)	Diffusion (h)	SP3 (h)
E1	-	1.15	1.16
E2	0.625	1.45	1.89
E4	8.21E5, 5.53E3, 0.625	2.25	3.05
E8	8.21E5, 5.53E3, 4, 0.625, 0.28, 0.14	4.58	-

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In deterministic neutron transport, spatial divisions and energy-group numbers directly affect accuracy and computational cost. These effects were studied using diffusion and SP3 approximations for the TRIGA Mark II reactor. A mesh-independence study was performed using five meshes with 3.34–11.40 million cells. Reactivity decreased slightly with mesh refinement, with a maximum deviation below 15 pcm. Consequently, the 3.34-million-cell mesh was chosen for the pin-by-pin case, and the same meshing parameters were applied to all spatial homogenization cases.

3.1. Effect of Updating MGXS with Different CR Positions

MGXS generation in OpenMC depends on the neutron spectrum and may vary with CR positions. If this variation is negligible, a single MGXS calculation suffices for all CR configurations. To investigate,

two cases were studied for the pin-by-pin and two-group models: one with a constant MGXS (starting with fully inserted rods while the SHIM moves), and one updating MGXS during CR movement. The SHIM was varied due to its larger reactivity worth, while REG and TRANS remained at 0.176 m and 0.47 m (fully withdrawn). SHIM positions tested were 0, 0.1, 0.176, 0.252, 0.328, and 0.404 m.

Figure 3. Effect of updating MGXS under various CR positions on reactivity; (a) diffusion; (b) SP3.

Using OpenMC as a reference (Figures 3a,b), updating MGXS has negligible effect at the 0.1 m SHIM position, but discrepancies grow as SHIM is further withdrawn. Updating MGXS with SHIM position improves reactivity predictions, with a maximum improvement of 9.1% (381.1 pcm) for diffusion and 8.6% (322.8 pcm) for SP3. Therefore, MGXS must be computed for each CR position.

3.2. Spatial Homogenization Results

While the pin-by-pin case accurately represents pin-level power, it is unclear if such fine spatial homogenization introduces larger discrepancies than coarser schemes. To investigate, six partitioning schemes from Sec. 2.2 were considered. Two energy groups were used due to their good predictive performance (Sec. 3.3), and all three CRs were kept fully inserted in all simulations.

As shown in Table II, the one-region homogenization method yields poor predictions of the k_{eff} in both methods, compared with the MC reference result (0.99905 ± 0.00017 ; -95.1 ± 17.0 pcm), likely due to underestimation of the fission MGXS when the large-volume water pool is homogenized with the core. The SP3 method performs even worse than the diffusion method, as discussed in Sec. 3.3. In contrast, the pin-by-pin homogenization method provides accurate predictions for both methods, with differences of 505.5 ± 17.0 pcm for diffusion and 295.4 ± 17.0 pcm for SP3 relative to MC results. The SP3 method nearly doubles the accuracy compared with the diffusion approximation. This improvement is expected, as all CRs are inserted into the core, and the diffusion method performs poorly with strong absorbers. For the other four partitioning schemes, finer spatial division generally improves k_{eff} despite less accurate predictions overall. The pin-by-pin case requires over one hour for pre-processing and an additional 1.4 and 1.8 hours of computation for the diffusion and SP3 methods, respectively.

3.3. Energy-Group Homogenization Results

To identify the appropriate number of energy groups in terms of accuracy and computational cost, a pin-by-pin model was employed in OpenFOAM for its strong predictive performance, as discussed in Sec. 3.2. The SHIM rod calibration curve was evaluated using different energy-group structures for the diffusion and SP3 methods, as shown in Table I and Sec. 2.3.

Table II. Comparison of eigenvalues and computational costs with different region divisions.

Division	Diff.	SP ₃	Diff. Δρ	SP3 Δρ	Pre-proc.	Diff. cost	SP3 cost
1 region	0.96317	0.96287	3729.1 pcm	3761.0 pcm	0.09 h	0.04 h	0.06 h
1 core	1.02470	1.027373	2505.9 pcm	2759.5 pcm	0.12 h	0.04 h	0.05 h
2 core	1.01549	1.01819	1620.7 pcm	1881.7 pcm	0.05 h	0.04 h	0.07 h
5 core	1.01817	1.02096	1879.4 pcm	2148.3 pcm	0.06 h	0.03 h	0.06 h
10 core	1.01657	1.01856	1725.0 pcm	1917.5 pcm	0.09 h	0.04 h	0.07 h
pin-by-pin	0.99403	0.99611	505.5 pcm	295.4 pcm	1.19 h	1.45 h	1.89 h

 Figure 4. Variation of k_{eff} with energy groups; (a) absolute value; (b) relative value between diffusion and SP3.

Figure 4 (a) shows the k_{eff} values for different energy-group structures, while Figure 4 (b) presents the relative differences between diffusion and SP3 methods, using SP3 as reference. In both methods, the two-group case agrees best with the MC reference, with maximum discrepancies of 549.1 pcm (24.7%) for diffusion and 516.5 pcm (23.3%) for SP3. Although these discrepancies remain noticeable, they are case-dependent, especially for such a complex application. In contrast, a difference of about 1000 pcm was reported for a simpler CROCUS reactor using GeN-FOAM [13]. In this energy structure, SP3 outperforms diffusion only at 0.0 m when the SHIM rod is fully inserted; its advantage diminishes as the rod is withdrawn. In the four-group case, both methods degrade, although SP3 is superior. The diffusion method degrades with more groups due to inter-group scattering. The computational cost also rises with more groups, and for the same groups, SP3 requires more time to converge (Table I).

To further assess discrepancies between two methods, k_{eff} was analyzed for five energy divisions at 0.404 m (SHIM). (Table III). Although the CR position affects absorption slightly ($<0.2\%$, Figure 4(b)), a large extraction position of 0.404 m was chosen to minimize absorption. Comparison with OpenMC predictions (1.04509 ± 0.00063 ; 4314.5 ± 57.7 pcm) shows: (1) increasing thermal groups improves accuracy in both methods (E1 and E2); (2) more high-energy groups increase discrepancies (E3 and E4); (3) finer divisions in both thermal and fast regions, even with coarse fast-region division (4 eV), worsen deviations (E5); (4) SP3 better captures anisotropic effects with finer high-energy divisions (E4). Generally, adding high-energy groups decreases k_{eff} , likely because resonance effects and complex inter-group scattering

complicate MGXS prediction. That explains the discrepancies between the two- and four-group cases. The SP3 method mitigates these discrepancies more effectively, though both methods perform worse than OpenMC for pin-by-pin model, as SP3 handles inter-group scattering more accurately.

Table III. Comparison of k_{eff} between Diffusion, SP3, and OpenMC for different group structures

Groups	Divisions [eV]	Diffusion	SP3	Diffusion $\Delta\rho$	SP3 $\Delta\rho$
E1	[0, 0.625, 2E7]	1.04146	1.04008	333.5 pcm (7.7%)	460.9 pcm (10.7%)
E2	[0, 0.28, 0.625, 2E7]	1.04157	1.04030	323.4 pcm (7.5%)	466.5 pcm (10.8%)
E3	[0, 0.625, 4, 2E7]	1.03816	1.03639	638.7 pcm (14.8%)	803.2 pcm (18.6%)
E4	[0, 0.625, 8E5, 2E7]	1.00101	1.00424	4213.6 pcm (97.7%)	3892.3 pcm (90.2%)
E5	[0, 0.28, 0.625, 4, 2E7]	1.03844	1.03664	612.8 pcm (14.2%)	780.0 pcm (18.1%)

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigated the effects of spatial and energy-group homogenization in deterministic neutron transport calculations using the TRIGA Mark II research reactor as a test case. OpenMC was used for MGXS generation and a complete TRIGA reactor model, including the water pool, was constructed.

The key findings were summarized below. Updating the MGXS for different CR positions improves accuracy in both methods, as the neutron spectrum—and thus MGXS generation in OpenMC—varies with CR position. Pin-by-pin case provides excellent k_{eff} predictions, and the SP3 method nearly doubles the accuracy with a difference of 295.4 ± 17.0 pcm different from OpenMC reference, compared with 505.5 ± 17.0 pcm of the diffusion method. This improvement is expected, as all CRs are inserted into the core, and the diffusion method is worse to predict strong absorbers. One-region homogenization shows significant discrepancies due to underestimation of fission MGXS when the water pool is homogenized with the core. Although the four intermediate spatial-homogenization cases are less accurate, they maintain high computational efficiency. Based on the pin-by-pin model, k_{eff} decreases with more energy groups; the two-group case performing best in both methods. The maximum discrepancies are 549.1 pcm (24.7%) for diffusion and 516.5 pcm (23.3%) for SP3 in calibration curves, with differences between the two methods below 0.2%; diffusion performs slightly better as the CR is withdrawn. For computational cost, the two-group pin-by-pin case requires only 0.30 hours of additional time for diffusion and 0.73 hours for SP3. Increasing thermal-energy divisions improves accuracy, whereas additional high-energy divisions reduce it due to stronger inter-group scattering and resonance effects. Nevertheless, SP3 outperforms diffusion in high-energy divisions, though both show larger deviations.

In summary, for such a compact asymmetric application, pin-by-pin spatial MGXS homogenization represents an appropriate choice for both methods. The classic two-group division with a cutoff of 0.625 eV provides a reasonable compromise. Although a slight improvement can be achieved by increasing the number of thermal groups, a potential convergence stability problem may arise. Finally, the diffusion method is sufficient for criticality calculations, whereas the SP3 method is strongly recommended in the presence of strong absorbers within the core. Future work will explore high-order scattering moments to improve accuracy and develop multi-physics models toward a digital twin of the TRIGA reactor.

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